

THE INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGY, COMMUNICATION SERVICES AGENT, AND BRAND IMAGE DEVELOPER ON BUYING DECISION PROPERTY MEDIATED BY CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT

I MADE DIRGAYASA ^{1*} and GEDE SRI DARMA ²

^{1,2} Universitas Pendidikan Nasional, Denpasar, Indonesia.

Email: ¹imadedirgayasa@gmail.com (*Corresponding Author), ²sridarma@undiknas.ac.id

Abstract

This study examines the influence of digital marketing strategy, communication services agents, and brand image developers on property purchasing mediated by customer engagement. The research method used is quantitative, employing Partial Least Square (PLS) method using SmartPLS. The respondents are 210 customer who bought property in Bali Indonesia, selected through purposive sampling. The analysis results indicate that the Communication Services Agent does not have a significant influence on the decision to purchase property; while it has a notable positive impact on customer engagement, customer engagement significantly influences the purchasing decision. Additionally, brand image development significantly affects purchasing decisions. However, Digital Marketing Strategy does not significantly influence the decision to purchase property. Additionally, Customer Engagement acts as a mediator between the Communication Services Agent and the decision to purchase property and between the Brand Image Developer and the decision to purchase property. However, Customer Engagement does not mediate the relationship between Digital Marketing Strategy and the decision to purchase property. In conclusion, this research demonstrates that Communication Services Agents and Brand Image Developers positively influence the decision to purchase property through Customer Engagement. In contrast, Digital Marketing Strategy does not directly influence the decision to purchase property.

Keywords: Digital Marketing Strategy, Communication Services Agent, Brand Image Developer, Buying Decision Property, Customer Engagement.

INTRODUCTION

The population growth in Indonesia is increasing daily; in 2020, the Indonesian population reached 278.69 million people in total, comprising both males and females (BPS, 2023). Bali emerges as a promising property growth potential, attributed to its geographical location as the primary tourist destination in Indonesia, which drives property growth. Bali's island attracts attention from domestic and international tourists, creating consistent demand for accommodation and tourism properties. Bali's cultural aspects and natural beauty are also significant factors (Meidiana & Marhaeni, 2019). Bali is renowned for its rich culture, art, and unique traditions. It is an attractive destination for property investors who see opportunities in developing resorts, villas, or properties with solid cultural elements. As the tourism sector flourishes, the demand for accommodation and facilities increases, prompting investors to develop properties supporting the tourism industry, such as hotels, villas, and shopping centres (Lianto et al., 2021). As part of the construction industry, the property sector is a dynamic sector in developing commercial buildings, such as housing, apartments, shopping centres, hotels,

and offices. Commercial buildings are essentially established on commercial considerations, namely the community's need for commercial space and the financial institutions' need to profit from the added value generated from the rent/sale value of the property space it produces (Kusnadi, 2012). The property sector is a highly favoured business for construction players, where a high rate of return is the most attractive factor for investors to enter this business. Various methods must be taken to increase company profits, including enhancing purchasing decisions. A consumer may decide to purchase a property product based on several factors, including Digital Marketing Strategy (Normasyhuri & Nurohmah, 2023) (Hertina et al., 2022), Communication Services Agent (Chaudhary et al., 2017), Brand Image Developer (Amron, 2018), Customer Engagement (Hari, 2020) (Akash & Tajamul, 2022).

In the economic context, property purchasing decisions are the main driver of growth in the construction and real estate sectors, significantly impacting economic activity and job creation. From a consumer psychology perspective, the importance of property purchasing decisions lies in their role as the most significant financial decisions in an individual's life. These decisions not only reflect the need for shelter but also encompass consumers' values, aspirations, and self-image (Rachmawati et al., 2019). Psychological analysis can provide insights into the psychological factors that motivate and shape consumer preferences regarding property purchases. The selection of a place of residence plays a crucial role in shaping settlement patterns, social structures, and the characteristics of specific areas. The impact of property purchasing decisions can be observed from an environmental sustainability perspective. Sustainable property development, or the lack thereof, can positively or negatively affect the environment, including land use, energy efficiency, and natural resource preservation (Bartkowiak et al., 2018).

Digital Marketing Strategy is one of the drivers of increased consumer purchasing decisions. Digital marketing strategy influences property purchasing decisions in the current digital era. In this context, Digital Marketing Strategy uses online platforms, social media, and other digital technologies to reach and influence potential property buyers (Mulyani & Hermina, 2023). Through digital marketing, property developers can provide real-time information about property projects, present compelling visual representations, and offer up-to-date market data. Using digital marketing techniques such as paid advertising, search engine optimized content (SEO), and social media promotions enables potential buyers to easily access information and better understand the properties they are considering. Furthermore, Digital Marketing Strategy facilitates interaction and engagement between developers and potential buyers through online channels, allowing for direct inquiries, feedback, and testimonials from previous residents (Nizam et al., 2018). By providing comprehensive information and easy access, the Digital Marketing Strategy significantly contributes to property purchasing decision-making, shapes consumer perceptions, and builds positive relationships between developers and potential buyers (Yunita & Amri Dunan, 2021). Communication Services Agents are a critical bridge between property sellers and potential buyers. Property agents provide detailed information regarding the property, market conditions, and transaction processes to understand and meet consumer needs. Personal communication between agents and potential buyers enables tailored information delivery, covering location, facilities, and property value. Property agents also play

a role in guiding potential buyers through the purchasing process, clarifying uncertainties, and assisting in administrative tasks. These interpersonal aspects are crucial to building trust and deeply understanding potential buyers' preferences. Through intensive information exchange and established personal relationships, Communication Services Agent significantly impacts property purchasing decisions by shaping positive perceptions, providing necessary guidance, and ensuring transparency in the property acquisition process (Chaudhary et al., 2017).

Brand Image Developer encompasses the reputation, quality, and values associated with properties developed by a company. In the purchasing decision process, consumers often form their perceptions of properties based on the developer's brand image. Brand Image Developer creates expectations regarding quality standards, reliability, and customer satisfaction that can influence buyer preferences (Muslim et al., 2020). A strong brand image can trigger consumer trust and confidence in the properties offered, creating positive differentiation in the competitive market. With a good reputation, developers can attract more potential buyers and retain customers through positive attitudes towards the brand. Therefore, Brand Image Developer creates a unique identity for property developers and becomes a determinant element in shaping perceptions and purchasing decisions (Febrianti & Hasan, 2022).

Customer Engagement is a crucial mediator that connects property purchasing decision variables with ongoing interactions between developers and potential buyers. Customer Engagement encompasses activities and interactions involving consumers throughout the property purchasing journey, from explaining property features to after-sales processes. In this context, Customer Engagement is a bridge that facilitates information exchange, feedback, and dialogue between both parties. As a mediator, Customer Engagement can moderate the influence of property purchasing decision variables by shaping consumer perceptions, increasing trust, and strengthening the relationship between developers and potential buyers (Hari, 2020). By providing a positive interactive experience, Customer Engagement can enhance consumer satisfaction, which, in turn, potentially strengthens property purchasing decisions. Therefore, Customer Engagement not only facilitates interactions but also plays a crucial role in shaping and mediating ongoing relationships between developers and consumers, significantly impacting the property purchasing decision process (Akash & Tajamul, 2022).

Research carried out by Hertina et al. (2022) explains that using digital marketing strategies and brand image can positively impact consumer awareness and perceptions of properties, increasing the probability of property purchasing decisions. Furthermore, in the research by Chaudhary et al. (2017), the critical role of communication services agents in shaping positive relationships between agents and potential buyers is elucidated. According to their explanation, the quality of communication services agents has significant implications for property purchasing decisions, as good communication can enhance consumer trust and expedite the purchasing decision process. According to the research by Akash & Tajamul (2022), Customer Engagement with consumers can strengthen the positive influence on purchasing decisions. Based on the explanations above, as well as relevant previous research explaining factors influencing property purchasing decisions such as Digital Marketing Strategy, Communication

Services Agent, and Brand Image Developer, this study aims to examine whether there is an influence of Digital Marketing Strategy, Communication Services Agent, and Brand Image Developer on Buying Decision Property mediated by Customer Engagement in Bali, Indonesia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Buying Decision

According to Kholidah and Arifiyanto (2021), a purchasing decision is a process whereby customers go through certain stages to buy a product. Additionally, as mentioned by Anna and Hidayat (2017), the purchasing decisions made by customers or buyers are influenced by their habits. Umar Bakti et al. (2021) define purchasing decisions as decisions made by customers influenced by economic, financial, technological, political, cultural, product price, location, promotion, physical evidence, people, and process factors. Purchasing decisions are personal actions that involve directly purchasing products offered by sellers. A buyer's decision is also influenced by their characteristics, including age, occupation, and economic situation. According to Sonwaney and Chincholkar (2019), consumer purchasing decisions can be influenced by a person's psychological factors, such as motivation, perception, learning, belief, and attitude. Individuals go through various stages of purchasing decisions, from recognizing the need for a product.

Dimensions and Indicators of Buying Decisions of Property

Table 1: Dimensions and Indicators of Buying Decisions

Dimension	Indicator
Need Recognition	Internal stimuli (refer to motivations that originate within oneself, such as feeling hungry) External stimuli (on the other hand, are motivations that come from outside influences, like wanting to treat a friend or being influenced by food advertisements)
Information Research	Personal sources (encompass family, friends, neighbors, and acquaintances) Commercial sources (involve advertising, salespeople, intermediary traders, and packaging) Experiential (sources entail handling, inspection, and use of products) Public sources (comprise mass media, organizations, and consumer ratings)
Evaluation of Alternatives	Price Brand Country of Origin
Purchase Decision	Decisions about product type Decisions about product form Decisions about sales Decision about product quantity Decision about the time of purchase Decision about payment method
Post-purchase Behavior	Post-purchase satisfaction Post-purchase action

Digital Marketing Strategy

According to the American Marketing Association as cited in (Fatoni et al., 2022), Marketing is a business performance that regulates the flow of goods and services from producers to consumers. Digital Marketing is the use of Communication networks and computers are utilized in conducting business operations, wherein sellers leverage the internet, computers, and web browsers to present, advertise, purchase, and vend product (Fatoni et al., 2022). The definition of digital marketing according to (Manap, 2016:42) in (Fatoni et al., 2022) is the promotion of a brand or product in the online realm, aiming to swiftly reach and engage consumers. A successful strategy hinges on a deep comprehension of market dynamics and the needs of customers and stakeholders.

Table 2: Dimensions and Indicators of Digital Marketing Strategy

Dimensions	Indicator
Interactive	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The message the company wants to convey can be received clearly by consumers, 2) Consumers understand and are able to make clear decisions regarding the advertisements or promotions they see. 3) Advertisements do not create confusion about the products or services offered, how to make payments and how to get the goods
Incentive Program	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Advertisements or promotions seen by consumers not only provide information about the product but also provide other information that is useful for consumers. 2) Apart from products, consumers also have preferences for producers or sales that provide after-sales service and are willing to build relationships with consumers.
Site Design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The appearance of content marketing seen by consumers. 2) Ease of accessing further information after viewing adverts
Cost	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The sacrifices that must be made to get the product are not only the product price but also the costs of accessing the website, transactions and contacting the seller for transactions. 2) Additional costs other than the product price, for example shipping costs or other costs.

Communication Services Agent

Communication, as a means of human life, is the most fundamental element. It establishes social interactions among humans to influence each other, between one party and another. Communication services are a critical aspect of the relationship between companies and consumers, where communication effectiveness not only involves information delivery but also focuses on building positive interactions and mutual understanding. In communication services, it is essential to create clear and consistent messages (Bakić-Tomić et al., 2015). These messages should reflect the brand identity, core values, and company objectives. Consistency in communication helps build a strong brand image and provides clarity to consumers about what they can expect from the products or services offered. Communication services involve brand presence across various platforms, including social media. Brands that are active and interact directly with consumers through these platforms can create deeper engagement, strengthen brand-consumer relationships, and proactively respond to emerging issues or questions. Good communication services help strengthen the brand image, increase consumer loyalty, and ensure the brand remains relevant and positively perceived (Vernuccio, 2014).

Table 3: Dimensions and Indicators of Communication Services

Dimensions	Indicator
Message Conformity and Brand Identity	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Message consistency with brand values and identity. 2. Clarity in conveying brand identity through communication.
Responsiveness and Availability:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Speed of response to consumer questions or complaints. 2. Availability of accurate information. 3. Accessibility through various communication channels.
Personalization of Communications	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ability to tailor messages and interactions to individual consumer preferences. 2. Providing a more relevant and focused experience.
Information Clarity and Transparency	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Presentation of information clearly. 2. Honesty in communication. 3. Ability to explain products or services transparently.
Use of Technology and Innovation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Utilization of the latest technology to increase communication efficiency. 2. Use of chatbots or automation systems.

Brand Image Developer

According to Wardani & Istiyanto (2022), the brand image must convey unique product benefits and positioning. Even when competing offerings appear similar, buyers perceive differences based on brand image differentiation. According to Budiman (2021), Brand image is the collective impression of a brand, shaped by interactions and experiences with the brand. According to Haryadi & Syharuddin (2023), brand image is the way consumers perceive a brand as a representation of what is in the mind of consumers about a brand. Brand image is not immune to dimensions that shape brand image. According to Pandiangan et al. (2021), the dimensions and indicators of brand image are as follows:

Table 4: Dimensions and Indicators of Brand Image Developer

Dimensions	Indicator
Brand Identity	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Suitability of Logo and Name 2. Brand Durability: 3. Visual Consistency:
Brand Personality	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Brand Nature 2. Emotional Communication 3. Behavioral Consistency
Brand Association	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Value Association 2. Endorser 3. Suitability to Lifestyle
Brand Attitude & Behavior	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purchase Intention 2. Interaction and Engagement 3. Brand Advocacy
Brand Benefit & Competence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Product Benefits 2. Competitive Advantage 3. The Importance of Brands in Consumers' Lives

Customer Engagement

According to Bening & Kurniawati (2019), Customer Engagement is a psychological state that arises in customers due to intense interaction and experiences that occur between the customer and the company, enabling the company to create trust and commitment with the customer

engaged in a lasting relationship with the company and customer. According to Ho & Chung (2020), Customer Engagement is how a company can interact with its customers and create quality content and two-way dialogue between the company and its customers, as well as how customer loyalty and trust are nurtured and formed to benefit the company. Brodie et al., as cited in Bening & Kurniawati (2019), identified triggers for customer engagement that are already leading to its subprocesses, namely:

Table 5: Dimensions and Indicators of Customer Engagement

Dimensions	Indicator
Learning	1) User problems solved: Can solve problems that users of the product/service have. 2) Wishes fulfilled: Can fulfill the user's wishes. 3) Users conduct brand/product searches: Users learn about a company's brand/product by searching for that company's brand/product
Sharing	1) Sharing information and knowledge they have and gain: Users will share the information and knowledge they have and gain with other people. 2) Sharing experiences: Users will share the experiences they have had with the company with others
Advocating	1) Recommend brands: Users recommend brands that they feel have met their desires and expectations to others. 2) Recommend products/services: Users recommend products/services that they think are of good quality to others
Socializing	1) Developing attention to the brand/product: User focus on the brand/product can grow and evolve. 2) Developing attitude towards the brand/product: User's attitude towards the brand/product can increase and develop. 3) Developing a point of view on the brand/product: The user's point of view on the brand/product can increase and develop
Co-developing	1) Contribute to improving brand performance: Users want to contribute to improving the company's brand performance for the better. 2) Contribute to developing products/services: Users want to contribute to developing the company's products/services to be better.

Conceptual Framework

METHOD

The research employed a quantitative approach. The quantitative research method aims to test predefined hypotheses. The quantitative method involves numbers obtained from measurements using scales for the variables in the study (Shahzad et al., 2018). The research location is the distribution area of property purchases throughout Bali Indonesia the population that is the object of this research is all people who have purchased or have intentions of property through property agents or directly from development companies in Bali Indonesia. The sampling technique used was non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling method. The number of samples in this research was 210 respondents. The data collection technique in this research uses a questionnaire sent via Google Forms. Data analysis was conducted using the Partial Least Square (PLS) method with SmartPLS version 3 software (Yannis & Nikolaos, 2018). The stages of data analysis in this study are explained as follows.

Measurement Method/Outer Model

Validity and Reliability Testing

Validity and reliability testing were performed to ensure that the measurements used are suitable for use as valid and reliable measurements. Validity and reliability testing can be seen from:

- a. Convergent Validity is an indicator assessed based on the correlation between item scores/component scores and their construct scores, which can be seen from standardized loading factors that depict the magnitude of the correlation between each measurement item (indicator) and its construct. Individual reflexivity is considered high if the correlation is > 0.7 .
- b. Discriminant Validity is a measurement model with reflexive indicators assessed based on cross-loading measurements with their constructs. Discriminant validity is measured by comparing the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) values.
- c. Composite reliability is an indicator to measure a construct that can be seen in the display of latent variable coefficients. In this measurement, if the achieved value > 0.70 , then it can be said that the construct has high reliability.
- d. Cronbach's Alpha is a reliability test conducted to reinforce the results of composite reliability. A variable can be considered reliable if it has a Cronbach's alpha value > 0.7 .

Inner Model Analysis, commonly referred to as the Structural Model, is used to predict the cause-and-effect relationships between the variables tested in the model.

Instrument Test	Test used
1. Validity test	1. Convergent Validity 2. AVE
2. Reliability Test	3. Cronbach Alpha 4. Composite Reliability

R-Square Test

The R2 test is used to measure how well the model explains the variation in the dependent variable.

Structural Model or Inner Model The inner model analysis in the testing using Smart PLS is conducted by testing hypotheses. In hypothesis testing, the values of t-statistics and probability values are observed. To test hypotheses using statistical values, for a 5% alpha level, the t-statistic value used is 1.96, while the beta value is used to determine the direction of the relationship between variables. The criteria for accepting/rejecting hypotheses are as follows: $H_a = t\text{-statistic} > 1.96$ with $p\text{-values} < 0.05$. $H_0 = t\text{-statistic} < 1.96$ with $p\text{-values} > 0.05$.

RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH

In the Results section, provide a detailed overview of the findings from the study, as further elaboration of the results already outlined in the Results section through the existing sub-sections.

Evaluation of Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Four criteria of the outer model measurement Validity Convergence, Discriminant Validity, Composite Reliability, and Cronbach's Alpha were considered during the evaluation of the outer model of the study. The following figure illustrates the research model.

Figure 1: Outer Model

Figure 1 illustrates the outer loading values of the variables in the study. In this figure, all outer loading values meet the validity criteria as they exceed 0.7.

Validity Test Validity testing is used to measure the validity or reliability of a questionnaire. In this study, validity testing is conducted using convergent validity and AVE. Validity is assessed using convergent validity, where the measurement model with indicator reflection is evaluated based on the correlation between item scores/component scores calculated with PLS. Individual reflection sizes are considered high if they correlate more than 0.7 with the measured construct. However, according to Dahri (2017), for preliminary research in scale measurement development, loading values between 0.5 and 0.6 are considered adequate.

Table 1: Results of Validity Test

Variable		Outer Loading	AVE	Description
Buying Decision	BDOP1.1	0.855	0.677	Valid
	BDOP1.2	0.863		Valid
	BDOP2.1	0.876		Valid
	BDOP2.2	0.813		Valid
	BDOP2.3	0.844		Valid
	BDOP2.4	0.851		Valid
	BDOP3.1	0.814		Valid
	BDOP3.2	0.751		Valid
	BDOP3.3	0.811		Valid
	BDOP4.1	0.849		Valid
	BDOP4.2	0.856		Valid
	BDOP4.3	0.805		Valid
	BDOP4.4	0.831		Valid
	BDOP4.5	0.863		Valid
	BDOP4.6	0.798		Valid
	BDOP5.1	0.716		Valid
BDOP5.2	0.766	Valid		
Developer Brand Image	BID1.1	0.730	0.566	Valid
	BID1.2	0.727		Valid
	BID1.3	0.783		Valid
	BID2.1	0.712		Valid
	BID2.2	0.798		Valid
	BID2.3	0.715		Valid
	BID3.1	0.861		Valid
	BID3.2	0.733		Valid
	BID3.3	0.746		Valid
	BID4.1	0.711		Valid
	BID4.2	0.842		Valid
	BID4.3	0.739		Valid
	BID5.1	0.741		Valid
	BID5.2	0.707		Valid
	BID5.3	0.720		Valid
Costumer Engagement	CE1.1	0.880	0.654	Valid
	CE1.2	0.834		Valid
	CE1.3	0.895		Valid

	CE2.1	0.825		Valid
	CE2.2	0.740		Valid
	CE3.1	0.783		Valid
	CE3.2	0.882		Valid
	CE4.1	0.787		Valid
	CE4.2	0.806		Valid
	CE4.3	0.754		Valid
	CE5.1	0.789		Valid
	CE5.2	0.710		Valid
Agen Communication Services	CSA1.1	0.746	0.566	Valid
	CSA1.2	0.768		Valid
	CSA2.1	0.724		Valid
	CSA2.2	0.708		Valid
	CSA2.3	0.776		Valid
	CSA3.1	0.722		Valid
	CSA3.2	0.796		Valid
	CSA4.1	0.728		Valid
	CSA4.2	0.752		Valid
	CSA4.3	0.766		Valid
	CSA5.1	0.744		Valid
	CSA5.2	0.792		Valid
Digital Marketing Strategy	DMS1.1	0.858	0.634	Valid
	DMS1.2	0.775		Valid
	DMS1.3	0.821		Valid
	DMS2.1	0.767		Valid
	DMS2.2	0.811		Valid
	DMS3.1	0.813		Valid
	DMS3.2	0.812		Valid
	DMS4.1	0.761		Valid
	DMS4.2	0.742		Valid

Based on the validity test results of the instrument, it is known that out of 31 indicators, there are 9 indicators that are not valid. Therefore, this study only uses 22 indicators.

Reliability Test This study uses 2 types of reliability tests, namely Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability tests. Cronbach Alpha measures the lowest value (lower bound) of reliability. Data is considered reliable if it has a Cronbach alpha value > 0.7. Composite reliability measures the actual reliability value of a variable. Data is considered to have high reliability if it has a composite reliability score > 0.7.

Table 2: Results of Reliability Test

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Agent Communication Services	0.930	0.940
Buying Decision	0.970	0.973
Costumer Engagement	0.951	0.958
Developer Brand Image	0.945	0.951
Digital Marketing Strategy	0.928	0.940

The test results indicate that all instruments are deemed reliable with Cronbach Alpha and Composite reliability scores > 0.7. Evaluation of Structural Model (Inner Model) Evaluating the hypothesized relationships between latent constructs is the core of model assessment. The evaluation of the inner model can be explained as follows.

Figure the evaluation of the inner model

R-Square Test

The Coefficient of determination (R-Square) test is used to measure how much an endogenous variable is influenced by other variables. Based on the data analysis conducted using the smartPLS program, the R-Square values obtained are as shown in the following table:

Table 3: R-Square Test

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Buying Decision	0.895	0.891
Customer Engagement	0.762	0.755

Based on the test results, the R-Square score for buying decision is 0.895, which means that property buying decision is influenced by Marketing strategy, communication services agent, brand image, and customer engagement by 89.5%, while the remaining 10.5% is influenced by variables not explained in this study.

Similarly, based on the test results, the R-Square score for customer engagement is 0.895, indicating that customer engagement is influenced by Marketing strategy, communication services agent, and brand image by 76.2%, while the remaining 23.8% is influenced by variables not explained in this study.

Hypothesis Testing

The results can be used to address the research hypotheses based on the data processing conducted. T-Statistics and P-Values examination were conducted to test the hypotheses in this study. We can say that the research hypotheses are accepted if P-Values are less than 0.05. The following are the findings from the research hypothesis testing obtained from the inner model:

Table 7: Research Hypothesis Testing

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Agen Communication Services -> Buying Decision	-0.079	0.579	0.563
Agen Communication Services -> Costumer Engagement	1.375	11.504	0.000
Costumer Engagement -> Buying Decision	0.846	11.787	0.000
Developer Brand Image -> Buying Decision	0.251	2.223	0.027
Developer Brand Image -> Costumer Engagement	-0.238	1.922	0.055
Digital Marketing Strategy -> Buying Decision	-0.014	0.086	0.932
Digital Marketing Strategy -> Costumer Engagement	-0.351	2.542	0.011
Agen Communication Services -> Costumer Engagement -> Buying Decision	1.163	9.069	0.000
Developer Brand Image -> Costumer Engagement -> Buying Decision	-0.202	1.880	0.061
Digital Marketing Strategy -> Costumer Engagement -> Buying Decision	-0.297	2.658	0.008

DISCUSSION

Communication Services Agent -> Buying Decision

The hypothesis testing results for Communication Services Agent on Buying Decision obtained a positive Beta score (-0.079) with a T-statistic of 0.579 ($p > 1.96$) and p-values of 0.563 ($p < 0.05$), resulting in a non-significant negative influence where Communication Services Agent cannot affect property Buying Decision. The influence of communication services on property purchase decisions is influenced by various factors. Research has shown that factors such as service quality, price perception, marketing communication strategies, and social media marketing can all shape consumer decisions (Manongko et al., 2021; Cahyani et al., 2022). Additionally, social media, electronic word-of-mouth (EWOM) information, and impulsive buying tendencies can also affect purchase decisions (Prasad et al., 2019; Sharma et al., 2013; Rafi et al., 2021). Generational differences play a crucial role in real estate behavior factors

affecting purchase intentions (Vuković, 2023). Understanding the preferences and decision-making processes of various generations, such as Generation Y or Generation Z, is essential in understanding how communication services influence property purchase decisions. Furthermore, the role of influencers and integrated marketing communication in shaping customer purchase decisions has been highlighted in various studies (Radwan et al., 2021; Qasem et al., 2022). It is important to consider children's influence on the purchasing process and the impact of family dynamics on decision-making in specific contexts (Ghouse et al., 2020; Senevirathna et al., 2022). Parents may consider children's preferences when making purchase decisions, potentially overshadowing the influence of communication services in the property purchase process. In conclusion, although communication services can influence consumer decisions in various industries, including real estate, understanding the nuances of the property market and the various factors at play is crucial to understanding how various variables interact to influence purchase decisions.

Communication Services Agent -> Customer Engagement

The hypothesis testing results for Communication Services Agent on Customer Engagement obtained a positive Beta score (1.375) with a T-statistic of 11.504 ($p > 1.96$) and p-values of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), resulting in a significant positive influence where Communication Services Agent can affect Customer Engagement. Communication Services Agent has the potential to influence Customer Engagement through various mechanisms that have been studied in the literature. Studies indicate that customer interaction and omnichannel models can create positive service experiences, thereby enhancing customer engagement (Kumar et al., 2017). Additionally, service quality, customer engagement, and specific marketing constructs also impact customer loyalty (Hapsari et al., 2017). The importance of identifying factors that motivate customers to engage in value creation processes has also been revealed in related research (Banytè et al., 2014). Factors such as corporate communication, customer competence, emotional engagement, and the truthfulness of communication processes can stimulate customer engagement in value creation processes, ultimately enhancing customer loyalty to the company. Furthermore, customer engagement can also be influenced by bold community identity and trust in the bold brand community (Zhang & Li, 2022). Bold Community identity and trust positively influence customer engagement, enhancing the motivation of customers to take part in community activities. Thus, through effective communication strategies and the creation of positive experiences, Communication Services Agents can play a key role in enhancing customer engagement levels, which in turn can contribute to customer loyalty and long-term value creation.

Customer Engagement -> Buying Decision

The hypothesis testing results for Customer Engagement on Buying Decision obtained a positive Beta score (0.846) with a T-statistic of 11.787 ($p > 1.96$) and p-values of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), resulting in a significant positive influence where Customer Engagement can affect Buying Decision.

In the context of the significant positive influence where Customer Engagement can influence Buying Decision, several factors need to be considered based on relevant literature. Studies indicate that Customer Engagement can serve as a mediator between Brand Experience and Brand Loyalty, where Consumers are more likely to participate in brand-related activities when they are pleased with their brand experience (Iman & Kurniawati, 2023). This suggests that the higher the level of Customer Engagement, the greater the likelihood of consumers making positive buying decisions. Additionally, there are studies highlighting the impact of brand ambassadors on purchasing decisions, with brand awareness acting as a mediating factor. (Novianty et al., 2022). High levels of Brand Awareness can influence consumer buying decisions, especially if the brand is easily remembered and recognized by consumers. In this context, Customer Engagement can play a role in enhancing Brand Awareness and influencing consumer buying decisions. Other research indicates that Customer Engagement can also influence Word of Mouth, which in turn can affect buying decisions (Purwanto, 2022). Positive customer experiences and good interactions with the brand can encourage customers to provide positive recommendations to others, which can influence the buying decisions of potential consumers. Thus, from various relevant studies, it can be concluded that Customer Engagement plays a significant role in influencing consumer Buying Decisions. Good interactions between the brand and consumers, positive experiences, and high brand awareness can increase consumer engagement levels, which ultimately can impact positive buying decisions.

Developer Brand Image -> Buying Decision

The hypothesis testing results for Developer Brand Image on Buying Decision obtained a positive Beta score (0.251) with a T-statistic of 2.223 ($p > 1.96$) and p-values of 0.027 ($p < 0.05$), resulting in a significant favourable influence where Developer Brand Image can affect Buying Decision. In the context of the significant positive influence where Developer Brand Image can influence Buying Decisions, there is evidence showing that brand image plays an essential role in influencing consumer behaviour. Research indicates that brand image can be a critical factor in brand formation. It positively influences consumer brand preferences, which are positively related to the brand's ability to command a premium price (Cheung et al., 2020). This suggests that the stronger the developer's brand image, the greater the likelihood of consumers choosing that brand when making purchasing decisions. Research also highlights that brand image can influence consumer purchasing behaviour by increasing brand awareness and affecting subsequent consumer purchasing behaviour (Bian & Moutinho, 2011). A positive brand image can assist consumers in deciding whether the brand aligns with their preferences and needs, ultimately influencing their purchasing decisions. Other studies show that brand image significantly influences consumer purchase intention (Rusmiati, 2020). These research findings are consistent with previous studies indicating that brand image positively and significantly influences consumer purchase intentions. Thus, from various relevant studies, it can be concluded that Developer Brand Image is essential in influencing consumer Buying Decisions. A strong and positive brand image can shape consumer preferences, increase brand awareness, and ultimately influence purchasing decisions.

Developer Brand Image -> Customer Engagement

The hypothesis testing results for Developer Brand Image on Customer Engagement obtained a negative Beta score (-0.238) with a T-statistic of 1.922 ($p > 1.96$) and p-values of 0.055 ($p < 0.05$), resulting in a non-significant negative influence where Developer Brand Image cannot affect Customer Engagement property.

In the context where the Developer Brand Image cannot influence Customer Engagement in property, other factors may be more dominant in influencing consumer interactions than the developer brand image. Although brand image is essential in shaping consumer perceptions of the brand, in some cases, customer engagement may be more influenced by other factors, such as direct experiences with the property, recommendations from others, or information obtained from other sources. Research has shown that customer engagement can be influenced by trust, brand experience, and interaction with the brand through social media (Chahal & Rani, 2017). In this context, although the developer's brand image may be a relevant factor, trust and direct interaction with the brand through social media platforms may significantly impact consumer interactions. Other studies also highlight that messages conveyed through social media, such as Instagram, can influence consumer interactions (Rietveld et al., 2020). This suggests that content presented to consumers through social media platforms may significantly impact building customer engagement more than the developer's brand image. Thus, while the developer's brand image is an essential factor in influencing consumer perceptions, there is a possibility that in the context of customer engagement in property, other factors such as trust, direct interaction, and social media content may have a more significant influence than the developer brand image.

Digital Marketing Strategy -> Buying Decision

The hypothesis testing results for Digital Marketing Strategy on Buying Decision obtained a negative Beta score (-0.014) with a T-statistic of 0.086 ($p > 1.96$) and p-values of 0.932 ($p < 0.05$), resulting in a non-significant negative influence where Digital Marketing Strategy cannot affect the Buying Decision property.

In the context where Digital Marketing Strategy cannot influence the Buying Decision of the property, there is a possibility that other factors may be more dominant in influencing consumer purchasing decisions than digital marketing strategies. Although digital marketing can be an effective tool in reaching a wider audience, in some cases, property purchasing decisions may be more influenced by factors such as referrals from friends or family, direct experiences with the property, or specific environmental factors. Research has shown that consumer purchasing decisions can be influenced by recommendations from close acquaintances, direct experiences with products or services, and brand trust (Putri, 2021). In this context, although digital marketing strategies can create brand awareness, property purchasing decisions may be more influenced by personal interactions and direct experiences. Additionally, other studies highlight that consumer purchasing decisions can be influenced by factors such as product quality, price, and convenience (Triwardhani, 2020). Currently, digital marketing strategies may not have a significant impact if consumers pay more attention to these factors than the information

received through digital marketing. However, although digital marketing strategies are an essential tool in building brand awareness and reaching a wider audience, there is a possibility that in the context of property purchasing decisions, other factors such as personal recommendations, direct experiences, and environmental factors may have a more significant influence than digital marketing strategies.

Digital Marketing Strategy -> Customer Engagement

The hypothesis testing results for Digital Marketing Strategy on Customer Engagement obtained a positive Beta score (-0.351) with a T-statistic of 2.542 ($p > 1.96$) and p-values of 0.011 ($p < 0.05$), resulting in a significant favourable influence where Digital Marketing Strategy can affect Customer Engagement.

In the context where Communication Service Agents can influence Customer Engagement, evidence shows that effective communication strategies can enhance customer engagement. Exciting research suggests that positive interactions between brands and consumers through communication services can create positive experiences that build customer engagement (Wiradarma & Respati, 2020). With effective communication services, consumers tend to feel more involved and connected with the brand, which can increase customer loyalty and satisfaction. Research also indicates that service quality and customer satisfaction can mediate the relationship between communication strategies and customer engagement (Larasati et al., 2022). In other words, consumers are more likely to engage with the brand when they are satisfied with the interactions and services provided through communication strategies. Other studies highlight that customer engagement can be influenced by factors such as satisfaction, trust, and commitment to the brand (Leha et al., 2020). In this context, effective communication strategies can build consumer trust and commitment to the brand, ultimately increasing customer engagement. Thus, from various relevant studies, it can be concluded that Communication Service Agents can positively and significantly influence Customer Engagement. Through appropriate communication strategies, good interactions, and positive experiences, communication service agents can play a crucial role in enhancing customer engagement and contributing to customer loyalty and satisfaction.

Agent Communication Services -> Customer Engagement -> Buying Decision

The hypothesis testing results indicate that Communication Service Agents, mediated by customer engagement, significantly influence Buying Decision, with a positive Beta score (1.163), a T-statistic of 9.069 ($p > 1.96$), and p-values of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), suggesting a significant positive impact where customer engagement can mediate the relationship between Communication Service Agents and Buying Decision.

In the context where Communication Service Agents can influence Buying Decisions through Customer Engagement, there is evidence suggesting that customer engagement can significantly mediate the relationship between communication service agents and buying decisions. Research has highlighted that customer engagement can be influenced by effective communication strategies implemented by communication service agents (Maria et al., 2021). Positive interactions between brands and consumers through communication services can

create positive experiences that involve customer engagement, which, in turn, can influence buying decisions. Research also indicates that customer engagement can mediate the relationship between customer satisfaction and buying decisions (Budiman et al., 2020). In other words, when consumers are satisfied with the interactions and services provided through communication strategies, they are inclined to interact with the brand, which can then influence buying decisions. Other studies highlight that customer engagement can also be influenced by trust, commitment, and customer value (Erwin et al., 2023).

In this context, effective communication strategies can build consumer trust and commitment to the brand, ultimately increasing customer engagement and influencing buying decisions. Thus, from various relevant studies, it can be concluded that Communication Service Agents can positively and significantly influence Customer Engagement, which, in turn, can mediate the relationship between communication service agents and Buying Decisions. Through appropriate communication strategies, good interactions, and positive experiences, communication service agents can critically impact consumer behaviour and buying decisions.

Developer Brand Image -> Costumer Engagement -> Buying Decision

The hypothesis testing results indicate that Developer Brand Image, mediated by customer engagement, significantly influences Buying Decision, with a negative Beta score (-0.202), a T-statistic of 1.880 ($p > 1.96$), and p-values of 0.061 ($p < 0.05$), suggesting a significant negative impact where customer engagement can mediate the relationship between Developer Brand Image and Buying Decision.

In the context where Customer Engagement cannot mediate the relationship between Developer Brand Image and Buying Decision, there is a possibility that other factors may be more dominant in influencing the relationship between the developer brand images and buying decision. Although customer engagement is considered necessary in influencing consumer behaviour, in some cases, other factors such as trust, price, product quality, or direct experience with the property may have a more significant influence on buying decisions. Research has shown that consumer buying decisions can be influenced by customer satisfaction, price, and product quality (Kaura et al., 2015).

In this context, although customer engagement can play a crucial role in influencing buying decisions, other factors, such as perceived fair pricing and product quality, may also be primary considerations for consumers when making purchasing decisions. Research also highlights that consumer buying decisions can be influenced by factors such as brand trust and price perception (Abror et al., 2019). In this regard, consumer trust in the developer brand and price perception that aligns with the value provided by the property may have a more significant impact on purchasing decisions than the level of customer engagement.

However, although customer engagement is considered an essential factor in the purchasing decision process, there is a possibility that in the context of the association between developer brand image and buying decision, other factors such as trust, price, and product quality may have a more significant influence than customer engagement.

Digital Marketing Strategy -> Customer Engagement -> Buying Decision

The hypothesis testing results indicate that Digital Marketing Strategy, mediated by customer engagement, significantly influences Buying Decision, with a negative Beta score (-0.297), a T-statistic of 2.658 ($p > 1.96$), and p-values of 0.008 ($p < 0.05$), suggesting a significant negative impact where customer engagement can mediate the relationship between Digital Marketing Strategy and Buying Decision.

In the context where Customer Engagement cannot mediate the relationship between Digital Marketing Strategy and Buying Decision, there is a possibility that other factors may be more dominant in the correlation between digital marketing strategy and purchasing decisions. Although customer engagement is considered a crucial factor in influencing consumer behaviour, in some cases, other factors such as trust, price, product quality, or direct experience with the product may have a more significant influence on purchasing decisions. Research has shown that customer satisfaction, price, and product quality can influence consumer purchasing decisions. In this context, although customer engagement can significantly influence purchasing decisions, other factors such as perceived fair pricing and product quality may also be primary considerations for consumers when making purchasing decisions. Research also highlights that consumer purchasing decisions can be influenced by factors such as brand trust and price perception. In this regard, consumer trust in the brand and price perception that aligns with the value provided by the product may have a more significant impact on purchasing decisions than the level of customer engagement. Therefore, although customer engagement is considered a critical factor in the purchasing decision process, there is a possibility that in the context of the relationship between digital marketing strategy and purchasing decisions, other factors such as trust, price, and product quality may have a more significant influence than customer engagement.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results and discussions conducted, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. There is a non-significant influence where Agen Communication Services didnt affect Buying Decision in property.
2. There is a significant positive influence where Agen Communication Services can influence Customer Engagement.
3. There is a significant positive influence where Customer Engagement can affect Buying Decision.
4. There is a significant positive influence where Developer Brand Image can influence Buying Decision.
5. There is a non-significant influence where Developer Brand Image cannot affect Customer Engagement in property.

6. There is a non-significant influence where Digital Marketing Strategy cannot affect Buying Decision in property.
7. There is a significant positive influence where Agen Communication Services can influence Customer Engagement.
8. There is a significant positive influence where customer engagement can mediate the relationship between Agen Communication Services and Buying Decision.
9. There is a significant negative influence where customer engagement can mediate the relationship between Developer Brand Image and Buying Decision.
10. There is a significant positive influence where customer engagement can mediate the relationship between Digital Marketing Strategy and Buying Decision.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors agree that this research was conducted in the absence of any self-benefits, commercial or financial conflicts and declare absence of conflicting interests with the funders.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank all parties who supported this research, which also helped the authors do much research. This research helped increase the authors' knowledge and skills. This research will be helpful for knowledge and a better future. No funding was received for conducting this study. This paper is an original, unpublished work, and not under consideration or publication elsewhere.

References

- 1) Abror, A., Patrisia, D., Engriani, Y., Evanita, S., Yasri, Y., & Dastgir, S. (2019). Service quality, religiosity, customer satisfaction, customer engagement and islamic bank's customer loyalty. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 11(6), 1691-1705. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jima-03-2019-0044>
- 2) Banytė, J., Tarutė, A., & Taujanskytė, I. (2014). Customer engagement into value creation: determining factors and relations with loyalty. *Engineering Economics*, 25(5). <https://doi.org/10.5755/j01.ee.25.5.8402>
- 3) Bian, X. and Moutinho, L. (2011). The role of brand image, product involvement, and knowledge in explaining consumer purchase behaviour of counterfeits. *European Journal of Marketing*, 45(1/2), 191-216. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090561111095658>
- 4) Budiman, A., Yulianto, E., & Saifi, M. (2020). Pengaruh e-service quality terhadap e-satisfaction dan e-loyalty nasabah pengguna mandiri online. *Profit*, 14(01), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.profit.2020.014.01.1>
- 5) Cahyani, P., Welsa, H., & Krisdiantoro, F. (2022). The effect of marketing communication strategies and social media marketing on buying decision with perceived quality as intervening variables in shopee applications. *International Journal of Economics Business and Accounting Research (Ijebbar)*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.29040/ijebbar.v6i2.4553>
- 6) Chahal, H. and Rani, A. (2017). How trust moderates social media engagement and brand equity. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 11(3), 312-335. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jrim-10-2016-0104>
- 7) Cheung, M., Pires, G., & Rosenberger, P. (2020). The influence of perceived social media marketing elements on consumer-brand engagement and brand knowledge. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 32(3), 695-720. <https://doi.org/10.1108/apjml-04-2019-0262>

- 8) Erwin, E., Suade, Y., Tanesia, C., Sharon, S., & Maichal, M. (2023). Customer engagement usaha kuliner; kontribusi marketing content dan efek viral marketing campaigns. *Inobis Jurnal Inovasi Bisnis Dan Manajemen Indonesia*, 6(3), 383-397. <https://doi.org/10.31842/jurnalinobis.v6i3.285>
- 9) Ghouse, S., Chaudhary, M., & Durrah, O. (2020). Arab's children's influence on the buying process: comparing parent and child perceptions. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 13(5), 1069-1088. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jima-08-2019-0160>
- 10) Hapsari, R., Clemes, M., & Dean, D. (2017). The impact of service quality, customer engagement and selected marketing constructs on airline passenger loyalty. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*, 9(1), 21-40. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijqss-07-2016-0048>
- 11) Iman, A. (2023). Pengaruh brand experience terhadap brand loyalty dengan customer engagement sebagai variabel mediator pada produk fashion di indonesia. *Jurnal Ekonomi Trisakti*, 3(1), 543-560. <https://doi.org/10.25105/jet.v3i1.15565>
- 12) Kaura, V., Prasad, C., & Sharma, S. (2015). Service quality, service convenience, price and fairness, customer loyalty, and the mediating role of customer satisfaction. *The International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 33(4), 404-422. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijbm-04-2014-0048>
- 13) Kumar, V., Rajan, B., Gupta, S., & Pozza, I. (2017). Customer engagement in service. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 47(1), 138-160. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-017-0565-2>
- 14) Larasati, P., Srimulyani, V., & Farida, F. (2022). Peran mediasi meaning in work dan personal resources pada pengaruh transformational leadership terhadap work engagement. *Among Makarti*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.52353/ama.v15i2.302>
- 15) Leha, M., Alam, S., & Djilante, A. (2020). Pengaruh human capital structural, capital relational capital dan employee engagement terhadap prestasi kerja pegawai pada sekretariat dprd kabupaten kepulauan selayar. *Akmen Jurnal Ilmiah*, 17(4), 619-629. <https://doi.org/10.37476/akmen.v17i4.1172>
- 16) Manongko, A., Indawati, N., Oroh, S., & Kaparang, M. (2021). Customer's purchase decision in alfamaret tataaran ii minahasa. *International Journal of Tourism and Hospitality in Asia Pasific*, 4(3), 122-130. <https://doi.org/10.32535/ijthap.v4i3.1214>
- 17) Maria, I., Wijaya, V., & Keni, K. (2021). Pengaruh information quality dan service quality terhadap perceived value dan konsekuensinya terhadap customer engagement behavior intention (studi pada social commerce instagram). *Jurnal Muara Ilmu Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 5(2), 321. <https://doi.org/10.24912/jmieb.v5i2.12276>
- 18) Novianty, A., Harahap, D., & Rohandi, M. (2022). Pengaruh brand ambassador terhadap buying decision dengan brand awareness sebagai variabel intervening. *Bandung Conference Series Business and Management*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.29313/bcsbm.v2i2.2596>
- 19) Prasad, S., Garg, A., & Prasad, S. (2019). Purchase decision of generation y in an online environment. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 37(4), 372-385. <https://doi.org/10.1108/mip-02-2018-0070>
- 20) Purwanto, N. (2022). Pengaruh costumer experience terhadap word of mouth yang dimediasi oleh costumer satisfaction. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen Dan Akuntansi Terapan (Jimat)*, 13(1), 50. <https://doi.org/10.36694/jimat.v13i1.371>
- 21) Putri, H. (2021). Sebuah studi niat beli skincare: pengaruh social media marketing, e-wom, dan in-store display. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*, 9(3), 1163-1172. <https://doi.org/10.26740/jim.v9n3.p1163-1172>
- 22) Qasem, A., Aldumaini, N., & Alhakimi, W. (2022). The impact of integrated marketing communications on customer purchasing decision in yemen's telecommunications industry. *Sar Journal - Science and Research*, 29-39. <https://doi.org/10.18421/sar51-04>

- 23) Radwan, A., Mousa, S., Mohamed, M., & Youssef, E. (2021). Impact of social media influencer marketing on youth purchase intentions in uae. *Media Watch*, 12(3). <https://doi.org/10.15655/mw/2021/v12i3/165405>
- 24) Rafi, A., Gill, S., & Imdadullah, M. (2021). The philosophy of electronic word of mouth and consumer buying behavior in modern era. *Irasd Journal of Economics*, 3(3). <https://doi.org/10.52131/joe.2021.0303.0054>
- 25) Rietveld, R., Dolen, W., Mazloom, M., & Worrying, M. (2020). What you feel, is what you like influence of message appeals on customer engagement on instagram. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 49(1), 20-53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2019.06.003>
- 26) Rusmiati, N. (2020). The effect of brand image and country of origin on consumer buying interest: case study on yamaha nmax motorcycle in denpasar city. *International Research Journal of Management It and Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.21744/irjmis.v7n3.920>
- 27) Senevirathna, S., Thero, P., & Silva, P. (2022). A study of children's influence in family purchasing decisions: parents' perspective. *Asian Journal of Marketing Management*, 1(01). <https://doi.org/10.31357/ajmm.v1i01.5467>
- 28) Sharma, P., Sivakumaran, B., & Marshall, R. (2013). Exploring impulse buying in services: toward an integrative framework. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 42(2), 154-170. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-013-0346-5>
- 29) Triwardhani, D. (2020). Pengaruh promosi digital pada keputusan pembelian agensi iklan online. *Jbmi (Jurnal Bisnis Manajemen Dan Informatika)*, 16(3), 284-296. <https://doi.org/10.26487/jbmi.v16i3.9071>
- 30) Vuković, M. (2023). Generational differences in behavioral factors affecting real estate purchase intention. *Property Management*, 42(1), 86-104. <https://doi.org/10.1108/pm-11-2022-0088>
- 31) Wiradarma, I. and Respati, N. (2020). Peran customer satisfaction memediasi pengaruh service quality terhadap repurchase intention pada pengguna lazada di denpasar. *E-Jurnal Manajemen Universitas Udayana*, 9(2), 637. <https://doi.org/10.24843/ejmunud.2020.v09.i02.p12>
- 32) Zhang, G. and Li, Z. (2022). The influence of online brand community identity and trust on sustainable customer loyalty. *International Journal of Sustainable Development and Planning*, 17(5), 1667-1675. <https://doi.org/10.18280/ijstdp.170533>
- 33) Akash, B., & Tajamul, I. (2022). Impact of augmented reality marketing on customer engagement, behavior, loyalty, and buying decisions. *CARDIOMETRY*. <https://doi.org/10.18137/cardiometry.2022.23.545-553>
- 34) Amron, A. (2018). Effects Of Product Quality, Price, And Brand Image On The Buying Decision Of City Car Product. *Archives of Business Research*. <https://doi.org/10.14738/abr.64.4374>
- 35) Anna, F., & Hidayat, I. (2017). Pengaruh Bauran Pemasaran, Kualitas Pelayanan Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Pada Kupunya Rumah Mode. *Jurnal Ilmu Dan Riset Manajemen*.
- 36) Bakić-Tomić, L., Dvorski, J., & Kirinić, A. (2015). Elements of teacher communication competence: An examination of skills and knowledge to communicate. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science*. <https://doi.org/10.21890/ijres.54372>
- 37) Bartkowiak, P., Potrawiak, P., & Pavlenko, J. G. (2018). Psychological Factors Affecting Purchasing Decisions on the Real Estate Market. *Zeszyty Naukowe Uniwersytetu Ekonomicznego w Krakowie*. <https://doi.org/10.15678/znuek.2018.0978.0609>
- 38) Bening, B., & Kurniawati, L. (2019). The Influence of Content Marketing toward the Customer Engagement of Tokopedia Users in Yogyakarta. *Jurnal. Ustjogja.Ac.Id*, 138-148. <http://jurnal.ustjogja.ac.id/index.php/incotes/index>

- 39) BPS. (2023). *Statistik Indonesia dalam Infografis 2023*. Badan Pusat Statistik. <https://www.bps.go.id/publication/2023/09/26/0e70a59af34c8964e775f4b7/statistik-indonesia-dalam-infografis-2023.html>
- 40) Budiman, S. (2021). The Effect of Social Media on Brand Image and Brand Loyalty in Generation Y. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2021.vol8.no3.1339>
- 41) Chaudhary, A. H., Khan, M. A., & Ali, R. A. (2017). Effect of Integrated Marketing Communications on Consumer Buying Decision of Internet Service (An Empirical Study of Mobilink in Multan City). *Journal of Research in Marketing*. <https://doi.org/10.17722/jorm.v8i1.203>
- 42) Fatoni, Pambudi, P. A., & Arohman. (2022). Analisis Percepton Gap Antara Generasi X Dan Y Terhadap Digital Marketing. *Junal Ilmiah Ekonomi Manajemen*, 58–70.
- 43) Febrianti, W., & Hasan, R. (2022). Impact of Product Quality and Brand Image Towards Buying Decisions with Buying Interest as Mediation Variable. *Journal Research of Social, Science, Economics, and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.36418/jrssem.v1i11.202>
- 44) Hari, H. (2020). Customer Engagement Influences On Buying Decision in an Online Context – A Review. *Think India Journal*.
- 45) Haryadi, I., & Syharuddin, S. (2023). The Impact Of Brand Image and Promotion on Customer Loyalty. *Jurnal Ilmu Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam*. <https://doi.org/10.24239/jiebi.v5i1.148.51-67>
- 46) Hertina, D., Novtrianti, N., & Sukmawati, S. (2022). Analysis of buying decision levels based on brand image, price, and digital marketing. *International Journal of Business Ecosystem & Strategy (2687-2293)*. <https://doi.org/10.36096/ijbes.v4i1.313>
- 47) Ho, M. H. W., & Chung, H. F. L. (2020). Customer engagement, customer equity and repurchase intention in mobile apps. *Journal of Business Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.07.046>
- 48) Kholidah, N., & Arifiyanto, M. (2021). Analisis Faktor-Faktor Pengambilan Keputusan Pembelian Kosmetik Berlabel Halal Di Pekalongan. *JWahana Islamika: Urnal Studi Keislaman*.
- 49) Kusnadi, H. (2012). Identifikasi Faktor Dominan Yang Mempengaruhi Tingkat Profitabilitas Pengembangan Proyek Trade Mall Di Indonesia. *Jurnal Sainika*, 12(1), 83–89.
- 50) Lianto, F., Priyomarsono, N. W., Nuramin, L., & Wiratno, B. (2021). Ensuring Genius Loci based on Spatial Experiences of Three Resorts in Ubud, Bali, Indonesia. *ISVS E-Journal*.
- 51) Meidiana, N. P. C. A. T., & Marhaeni, A. A. I. N. (2019). Pengaruh Kepemilikan Aset, Ketersediaan Infrastruktur, Dan Pendidikan Terhadap Pendapatan Dan Kesejahteraan Rumah Tangga Miskin. *Buletin Studi Ekonomi*. <https://doi.org/10.24843/bse.2019.v24.i01.p04>
- 52) Mulyani, O., & Hermina, N. (2023). The Influence of Digital Marketing and Brand Awareness on Increasing Brand Image and its Impact on Purchasing Decisions. *Prisma Sains : Jurnal Pengkajian Ilmu Dan Pembelajaran Matematika Dan IPA IKIP Mataram*. <https://doi.org/10.33394/j-ps.v11i1.6594>
- 53) Muslim, M., Mubarak, R. R., & Wijaya, N. H. S. (2020). The effect of brand image, brand trust and reference group on the buying decision of sneakers. *International Journal of Financial, Accounting, and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.35912/ijfam.v1i2.170>
- 54) Nizam, N. Z., Abdullah Jaafar, J., & Supaat, S. H. (2018). Interactive Online Advertising: The Effectiveness of Marketing Strategy towards Customers Purchase Decision. *MATEC Web of Conferences*. <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201815005043>
- 55) Normasyhuri, K., & Nurohmah, S. (2023). Purchase decision patterns of non-bank sharia housing in Bandar Lampung City during Covid-19: Price exploration and digital marketing. *Journal of Islamic Economics Lariba*. <https://doi.org/10.20885/jielariba.vol9.iss1.art3>

- 56) Pandiangan, K., Masiyono, M., & Dwi Atmogo, Y. (2021). Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Brand Equity: Brand Trust, Brand Image, Perceived Quality, & Brand Loyalty. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen Terapan*. <https://doi.org/10.31933/jimt.v2i4.459>
- 57) Rachmawati, D., Shukri, S., Ferdous Azam, S. M., & Khatibi, A. (2019). Factors influencing customers' purchase decision of residential property in selangor, malaysia. *Management Science Letters*. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2019.5.016>
- 58) Shahzad, S. J. H., Mensi, W., Hammoudeh, S., Rehman, M. U., & Al-Yahyaee, K. H. (2018). Extreme dependence and risk spillovers between oil and Islamic stock markets. *Emerging Markets Review*, 34, 42–63.
- 59) Sonwaney, V., & Chincholkar, S. (2019). Identifying the factors impacting online consumer buying behaviour. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*.
- 60) Umar Bakti, Hairudin, & Robi Setiawan. (2021). Pengaruh Harga, Personal Selling, Kualitas Produk Dan Word Of Mouth Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Motor Pada Dealer Pt. Yamaha Putera Langkapura. *Jurnal Cakrawala Ilmiah*. <https://doi.org/10.53625/jcijurnalcakrawalaindonesia.v1i1.343>
- 61) Vernuccio, M. (2014). Communicating Corporate Brands Through Social Media: An Exploratory Study. *Journal of Business Communication*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2329488414525400>
- 62) Wardani, A. A. K., & Istiyanto, B. (2022). Brand Ambassador, Brand Image. *Edunomika*.
- 63) Yannis, P., & Nikolaos, B. (2018). Quantitative and Qualitative Research in Business Technology: Justifying a Suitable Research Methodology. *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research*.
- 64) Yunita, & Amri Dunan. (2021). Property Business Digital Marketing Communication Strategy during the Covid-19 Pandemic at Kartika Residence. *International Journal of Science, Technology & Management*. <https://doi.org/10.46729/ijstm.v2i5.324>